

Data Management Plan for the LZP FLPP Project Optical Neural Networks Leveraging Synthetic Dimension (DIMENSION) (Nr. Izp-2024/1-0612)

Version 1

Description

This DMP serves as a comprehensive guide for managing the data generated during the DIMENSION project. This project focuses on fundamental research of synthetic dimension physics. The DMP outlines how we will handle, store, share, and preserve the data collected, ensuring it supports the project's objectives and is accessible for future research and development. The DIMENSION project will generate and collect a variety of data crucial for advancing optical neural networks (ONNs) technology. Specifically, the datasets will include data sets used for training, validating, and testing ONNs. The data will also be stored in various formats, e.g., CSV.

Data will be collected using sophisticated signal processing tools and optical measurement equipment. All data will be initially stored in raw format to ensure no initial data loss and then processed for analysis. In line with our commitment to advancing knowledge in the field of optical communications, the processed data will be made available to the research community. A dedicated data manager will oversee the implementation of this DMP, assisted by the project team. Responsibilities for data collection, processing, analysis, and sharing will be clearly defined within the project team to ensure adherence to the plan.

Funder

Latvijas Zinātnes padome

Grant

Izp-2024/1-0612

Researchers

Oskars Ozolins (0000-0001-9839-7488)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for the LZP FLPP Project Optical Neural Networks Leveraging Synthetic Dimension \(DIMENSION\) \(Nr. Izp-2024/1-0612\)](#)

Description:

This DMP serves as a comprehensive guide for managing the data generated during the DIMENSION project. This project focuses on fundamental research of synthetic dimension physics. The DMP outlines how we will handle, store, share, and preserve the data collected, ensuring it supports the project's objectives and is accessible for future research and development. The DIMENSION project will generate and collect a variety of data crucial for advancing optical neural networks (ONNs) technology. Specifically, the datasets will include data sets used for training, validating, and testing ONNs. The data will also be stored in various formats, e.g., CSV.

Data will be collected using sophisticated signal processing tools and optical measurement equipment. All data will be initially stored in raw format to ensure no initial data loss and then processed for analysis. In line with our commitment to advancing knowledge in the field of optical communications, the processed data will be made available to the research community. A dedicated data manager will oversee the implementation of this DMP, assisted by the project team. Responsibilities for data collection, processing, analysis, and sharing will be clearly defined within the project team to ensure adherence to the plan.

Researchers:

[Oskars Ozolins \(0000-0001-9839-7488\)](#)

Organizations:

[Riga Technical University](#)

Contact: [Ozoliņš Oskars \(oskars.ozolins@rtu.lv\)](mailto:Ozoliņš Oskars (oskars.ozolins@rtu.lv))

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvijas Zinātnes padome](#)

Grants: [lzp-2024/1-0612](#)

Project: [Optical Neural Networks Leveraging Synthetic Dimension \(DIMENSION\)](#)

3. License

License: [c](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-04-30](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[Data Management Plan for the LZP FLPP Project Optical Neural Networks Leveraging Synthetic Dimension \(DIMENSION\) \(Nr. lzp-2024/1-0612\)](#)

This DMP serves as a comprehensive guide for managing the data generated during the DIMENSION project. This project focuses on fundamental research of synthetic dimension physics. The DMP outlines how we will handle, store, share, and preserve the data collected, ensuring it supports the project's objectives and is accessible for future research and development. The DIMENSION project will generate and collect a variety of data crucial for advancing optical neural networks (ONNs) technology. Specifically, the datasets will include data sets used for training, validating, and testing ONNs. The data will also be stored in various formats, e.g., CSV.

Data will be collected using sophisticated signal processing tools and optical measurement equipment. All data will be initially stored in raw format to ensure no initial data loss and then processed for analysis. In line with our commitment to advancing knowledge in the field of optical communications, the processed data will be made available to the research community. A dedicated data manager will oversee the

implementation of this DMP, assisted by the project team. Responsibilities for data collection, processing, analysis, and sharing will be clearly defined within the project team to ensure adherence to the plan.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data will be collected using sophisticated signal processing tools and optical measurement equipment. All data will be initially stored in raw format to ensure no initial data loss and then processed for analysis. In line with our commitment to advancing knowledge in the field of optical communications, the processed data will be made available to the research community. A dedicated data manager will oversee the implementation of this DMP, assisted by the project team. Responsibilities for data collection, processing, analysis, and sharing will be clearly defined within the project team to ensure adherence to the plan.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- Others

MAT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Other scientists working on ONNs.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

Data will be collected using sophisticated signal processing tools and optical measurement equipment. All data will be initially stored in raw format to ensure no initial data loss and then processed for analysis. In line with our commitment to advancing knowledge in the field of optical communications, the processed data will be made available to the research community. A dedicated data manager will oversee the implementation of this DMP, assisted by the project team.

Responsibilities for data collection, processing, analysis, and sharing will be clearly defined within the project team to ensure adherence to the plan.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

